

distortion and spikelet whitening and sterility.

H. ganglbaueri has been found in Hooghly, Midnapore, Burdwan, and 24 Parganas districts of West Bengal. On wet season rice, damage occurs Sep-Oct; on dry season rice, maximum thrips concentration occurs in Mar-Apr.

***Nymphula africalis*, azolla pest in Nigeria**

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Insect damage reportedly limits azolla production as a supplementary N source for rice in many Asian countries. We observed high infestations of caseworm *Nymphula africalis* Hampson on *Azolla pinnata* in the 1986 wet season in multiplying tanks at Badeggi, Nigeria. We also observed high incidence on the Institute's farm at Badeggi.

The larvae were reared in the laboratory and the adult identified by the Commonwealth Institute of Entomology, London, as *Nymphula africalis*.

This is the first report of this species on azolla in Nigeria. Nymphs and adults of *Tramea* sp. (Odonata: Libellulidae) were predators of both larvae and adults of *N. africalis*.

Occurrence of a predatory mite *Pyemotes ventricosus* on *Sitotroga cerealella* Oliv.

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A predatory mite *P. ventricosus* (Newport) has been reported to prey on the larvae of rice moth *Corcyra* sp., Angoumois grain moth *Sitotroga cerealella* Oliv., satin moth *Stilpnotia salicis* L., peach twig borer *Anarsia lineatella* Zeller, bud moth *Spilonota ocellana* Schiff, and coconut caterpillar

Opisina arenosella (Wlk). Females feed by piercing the integument with their chelicerae. Mite eggs develop inside the female which gives birth to nymphs. The mite reproduces parthenogenetically.

P. ventricosus mites were mounted in Hoyer's medium on microscopic slides and kept in a hot air oven at 50°C for 2 d. Taxonomic characters were examined under a phase contrast microscope.

In the genus *Pyemotes*, the idiosoma are oval-shaped and the anterior edge of the dorsal propodosomal shield partially

overhangs the gnathosoma. In the female, legs I have five free segments terminating in a claw. Legs II to IV terminate in two claws and a pretarsus. In the male, tarsus IV bears a single claw. *P. ventricosus* characters agree with this description.

This mite has been a problem in maintaining insect cultures in the laboratory and is said to cause dermatitis in people handling infected storage materials.

Effect of 8 insecticides on rice bug eggs

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Twenty adults each sex of rice bug *Leptocoris oratorius* (Fabricius) were collected from the field and released on flowering rice plants confined in

cylindrical polyester cages. The leaf portions containing eggs were clipped and 30 eggs placed on moist filter paper in a petri dish. Insecticide was sprayed with an atomizer at a pressure of 0.7 kg/cm². Treatments were replicated three times. Nymphs that emerged were counted daily from 6 to 10 d after treatment.

Fenthion had the maximum ovicidal action, with 74% reduction in hatching followed by chlorpyrifos (see table).

Ovicidal effect of insecticides. Coimbatore, India.

Insecticide	Formulation	Rate (kg ai/ha)	Egg hatch reduction ^a (%)
Fenthion	100 EC	0.50	74 a
Chlorpyrifos	20 EC	0.20	60 ab
Phosphamidon	85 SC	0.50	55 bc
Phosalone	35 EC	0.35	44 c
Monocrotophos	36 SC	0.40	29 d
Quinalphos	25 EC	0.38	22 de
Malathion	50 EC	0.25	18 de
Endosulfan	35 EC	0.35	11 e

^aMeans followed by a common letter are not significantly different at 5% level, Duncan's multiple range test. Mortality corrected by Abbott's formula.

Rice leaf folder (LF) species in North Arcot District, Tamil Nadu

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Rice LF has been a major pest in Tamil Nadu for 15 yr. We surveyed North Arcot District during Sep-Jan (late samba) to identify LF species on rice.

In each division, 100 larvae were collected and reared in the glasshouse.

Rice LF genera in North Arcot District, Tamil Nadu, India.

Division	Generic composition (%)	
	<i>Cnaphalocrocis medinalis</i>	<i>Marasmia patnalis</i>
Arakonam	34	66
Cheyar	64	36
Gudiyatham	79	21
Thiruvannamalai	83	17
Vaniyambadi	31	69
Vellore	74	26
Walajah	7	93
Mean	53	47